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Effect of Concept Mapping Instructional Strategy on Performance in Agricultural Science among Senior Secondary School Students in Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study was carried out to determine the influence of concept mapping method on the academic performance of agricultural science students in senior secondary schools in Kaduna State. The study has 2 specific objectives, with corresponding 2 research questions and 2 null hypotheses respectively guided the study. The Research design adopted for this study is pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design. The population for this research comprised of all the agricultural science students in the 2021/2022 academic session in all the government senior secondary schools in Kaduna State. Multistage Sampling technique was used in selecting both schools and students. Eighty (80) (40 male & 40 Female) SS II students were randomly selected using hat and draw technique. Forty (40) male and forty (40) female students were selected. The instrument used for data collection was a multiple-choice test consisting of a 30-item Achievement Test in Agricultural Science (ATAS) which was developed by the researcher. Simple descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) were used to answer all the research questions and Data collected was then subjected to t-test statistics to determine students' academic performance under concept mapping method. All test null hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significance. Result indicated findings revealed that, students taught Agricultural Science using concept mapping method performed better than students taught using the conventional lecture method. Male students were found to perform better than their female counterparts in the concept mapping method instructional strategy. Concept mapping method should be adopted by agricultural science teachers as it enhances students' academic performance. Government should equip the schools with the necessary equipment and materials needed by teachers for effective utilization of concept mapping teaching method. Teachers should creative and use their initiative one using concept mapping method for better understanding by students and better academic performance.

Keyword: Concept Mapping, Instructional, Strategy, Performance, Agricultural Science

Introduction

Teachers are always looking for innovative ways and instructional methods to help students improve their outcomes in subject matter. Learning is a purposeful, conscious and complex process (Jones & Watson 2018). An important feature of learning is that it involves a complex interactive system including environmental, social, motivational, emotional and cognitive factors (Kamoru, 2021). Various teaching-learning strategies have been developed to accelerate learning process of students. Learning strategies evolve from the learning theories defining the role of teacher, students and the contents. In Nigeria, at present, mostly behavioural practices are in vogue in schools where students are passive and classroom environment is mostly teacher dominated (Baba, 2021). The effect of teaching methods on students' performance is receiving considerable attention from educators and researchers worldwide. What students learn is greatly influenced by how they are taught (Sani, 2017). Instructors teaching agricultural science have implemented a wide variety of teaching methods that fit different niches within the agricultural classroom. Muhammad, Abdullahi, Osman, Ali, Abu-Samah, Jumaat, Ashari and Umar, (2020), noted that there has been drastic reduction in the standard of students' performance at all levels of education in Nigeria in the past decades. The fall in the standard of education is traceable to many factors which are rooted in psychological and environmental factors. This fall in standard of performance at secondary level is incontrovertibly attributable to instructional methods adopted by teachers in schools. Sani (2017) stresses that learning through some methods is passive rather than active. Educators and researchers have repeatedly acknowledged the drawbacks of teaching with a strict lecture format.

Teaching methods according to Kamoru (2021) are the approaches, ways and strategies that a teacher adopts in conducting his lesson to a successful end. Muhammad, Abdullahi, Osman, Ali, Abu-Samah, Jumaat, Ashari and Umar, (2020)

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also defines teaching methods as the ways of teaching which involve a series of teacher directed activities that result into pupils' learning. Teaching methods comprise of principles and strategies used for instruction (Muhammad, Abdullahi, Osman, 2021). Teaching methods are the tools of the teacher for reaching the set goals and objectives. A concept map is a type of graphic organizer used to help students organize and represent knowledge of a subject. Concept maps begin with a main idea (or concept) and then branch out to show how that main idea can be broken down into specific topics. Concept maps are typically hierarchical, with the subordinate concepts stemming from the main concept or idea. This type of graphic organizer however, always allows change and new concepts to be added. They include **concepts**, usually enclosed in circles or boxes of some type, and **relationships** between concepts indicated by a connecting line linking two concepts. According to Muhammad, Mukhtar, Abdullahi and Hassan (2022), a concept map is a diagram showing the relationships among concepts. It is a graphical tool for organizing and representing knowledge. The concept map representation encodes propositions describing two or more concepts and their relationships, in implied natural language sentences. In educational settings, concept mapping exercises have been used to encourage students to actively construct an understanding of concepts and relationships within domains of interest (Ahmad, 2013). It was designed to support the learner's effort by externalizing concepts and propositions known to the student, making them visually apparent to facilitate their connection with newly acquired concepts. Concept maps have been used by teachers to assess students' understanding, by students to compare their knowledge and collaboratively renew their understanding, and by experts as a vehicle for modeling and sharing their knowledge. When created correctly and thoroughly, concept mapping is a powerful way for students to reach high levels of cognitive performance. Sani (2017) opined that, a concept map is also not just a learning tool, but an ideal evaluation tool for educators measuring the growth of and assessing student learning. As students create concept maps, they reiterate ideas using their own words and help identify incorrect ideas and concepts; educators are able to see what students do not understand, providing an accurate, objective way to evaluate areas in which students do not yet grasp concepts fully. Concept mapping is a valuable visual learning and thinking technique that helps students understand and communicate a concept and its connections between examples and ideas. Sani (2017) stated that, concept mapping is a valuable theory of learning that teachers can use to evaluate a student's level of understanding. A concept map is meant to be constantly changed, added to and reconstructed as new information and knowledge is learned (which is why it's usually easier to concept map using a computer); the goal is to have the student be able to explain each part of the concept map and their reasoning behind the concepts and connections they made.

Students' academic performance refers to students' achievement in the topic taught base on the stated objectives. The use of appropriate teaching method by the teacher helps to achieve this goal. Sani (2017) defines academic performance as the outcome of education which reveals the extent to which a student, teacher or institution have achieved their educational goals. Academic performance or achievement is commonly measured by examinations or continuous assessment (Sequeira, 2013). Considering the central role played by agriculture in the Nigerian economy, it is necessary to identify and apply teaching methods most appropriate for the subject in senior secondary schools. This is because, according to Daluba (2013), the objectives of agricultural science in secondary schools can only be attainable through effective instruction and motivation of students by agricultural science teachers. Abdulhamid (2013) also maintains that, for effective teaching to take place, the teacher must stimulate, encourage and maintain active participation of the students through the selection of appropriate teaching methods. This would require a balance between what is taught and how it is taught. Thus, successful teaching of agricultural science does not depend only on the teacher's mastery of the subject matter but also the teaching method employed.

The poor academic performance of students in agricultural science in both internal and external examinations has assumed a dangerous dimension. In light of this, agricultural science educators need to seek suitable ways of tackling the current mass failure if they are to halt the drifts of students to arts and social science subjects (Sani, 2017). Time has come when young men and women should learn in school how to maintain and improve the fertility of the soil, how to increase the yield of an economic plant and how to raise domesticated animals on a more economic basis. This is imperative because, school boys receiving lessons on agricultural science today will be the scientific farmers of the future. It is therefore the work of agricultural science teachers to teach students the scientific principles underlying the field of agriculture. According to Muhammad, et'al (2022), meaningful learning of principles depends on the ability of the pupils to recognize their relevance and their applicability to appropriate situations and then to apply them correctly. More so, the transfer of principles is a complex mental operation which cannot be left to chance. Students learning ability is greatly influenced by how they are taught. Instructors teaching agricultural science curricula have implemented a wide variety of teaching methods which fit different niches within the agricultural classroom (Abdulhamid 2013). Some methods of teaching are completely out of phase with background and local environments of the learners. Abdulhamid (2013), stressed that organizing for effective teaching in agricultural science is centered on certain factors such as what to teach, when to teach and how to teach. The teacher does not only teach the most

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relevant, meaningful and useful materials for specific students, he must also recognize and adopt a good and well-researched method of teaching that guarantees better understanding and also stimulates and motivates the students. Therefore, this study set out to investigate if the use of concept mapping method could yield a better performance of both male and female agricultural science students in senior secondary schools.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of the study is to determine the effects of concept mapping method on students' academic performance in agricultural science in senior secondary schools in Kaduna State. Specifically, the study intends to:-

1. Determine the difference in the academic performance of in agricultural Science among senior secondary students taught using concept mapping method instructional strategy and those in the exposed to lecture method control group
2. Determine the difference in the academic performance in agricultural science of among male and female Agricultural Science senior secondary students taught using exposed to concept mapping method Instructional Strategy.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference in the academic performance of agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group?
2. What is the difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the academic performance of Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group
2. There is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method

Methodology

The Research design adopted for this study is pre-test post-test quasi-experimental design. This design was suitable for this research as it allowed the researcher to collect data on students' academic performance using under the concept mapping instructional strategy on experimental group and lecture method and the on control group. To apply this design, the researcher gave the pre-test to students to determine their initial equivalence in all relevant aspects of the topic (Sheep and Goat Management systems) before exposing them to the treatment variables (concept mapping Method) after which post-test was taken administered. The population for this research comprised of all the agricultural science students in the 2021/2022 academic session in all the government senior secondary schools in Kaduna State. Multistage Sampling technique was used in selecting both school and students. One school was selected randomly from all the senior secondary schools in Kaduna State. The instrument used for data collection was a multiple-choice test consisting of a 30-item Achievement Test in Agricultural Science (ATAS) which was developed by the researcher. This is in line with Edinyang (2012) and Abdulhamid and Daluba (2013) who all adopted the same instrument in their studies. The test items were selected from livestock management system (sheep and goat). Each of the items had five (5) options, A-E. All instruments were pilot tested and were adjusted before administration. Data collection phase lasted for three weeks. Students were divided into two (2) groups; namely group A and B. Group A students formed the experimental group and were taught using concept mapping method. Group B formed the control group and were taught using traditional method. However, pre-test was given for both the treatment (group A) and the control (group B) group to test their initial equivalence before exposing group A to the treatment variable (concept mapping method). After the experiment, post-test was administered for both the treatment and the control groups. The exercise lasted for three weeks. Simple descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) were used to answer all the research questions. Data collected was then subjected to t-test statistics to determine students' academic performance under concept mapping method. All null hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the academic performance of agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group?

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Table 1: Difference in the academic performance of agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group

Group	N	SD	X	Grade
Concept Map.	40	2.312	67	B
Control Group	40	2.503	48	D

Result in Table 1 above indicated that, students taught using concept mapping method performed better than students in the control group who were taught using traditional lecture method. The mean score of students in the concept mapping method is 67 which is greater than the mean score of students in the control group (48). The mean grade of students in the concept mapping method is 'B' while that of students in the control group is 'D'. This implies that, concept mapping method leads to better students' academic performance in agricultural science in senior secondary schools.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method?

Table 2: difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method

Group	N	SD	X	Grade
Males	20	1.902	68	B
Females	20	2.021	65	B

Table 2 presents the result of male and female students taught using concept, mapping method. The result revealed that, male students performed better than their female counterparts when exposed to concept mapping method. The mean score of male students is 68 while that of their female counterparts is 65 indicating that, male students performed better than their female counterparts. However, mean grade of male students is 'B' while that of female students is also 'B' indicating that, the difference in the academic performance of male and female agricultural science students taught using concept mapping method is not much.

Test of Null Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the academic performance of Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group

Table 3: t-test analysis of the difference in the academic performance of agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group

Group	N	X	DF	t-cal.	t-crit.	Decision
Concept Map	40	67	78	3.21	1.9	rejected
Control Group	40	48				

The t-test analysis of the difference in the academic performance of agricultural science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group as presented in Table 3 indicated that, t-calculated (3.21) is greater than t-critical at the degree of freedom of 78 and at 5% level of significance. This implies that, there significant difference in the academic performance of Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant difference in the academic performance of agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method and those in the control group was rejected.

Hypothesis 2

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There is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method.

Table 4: t-test analysis of the difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method

Group	N	X	DF	t-cal.	t-crit.	Decision
Males	20	68	38	1.82	2.0	retained
Females	20	65				

Table 4 presents the t-test analysis of the difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method. The Table revealed that, t-calculated (1.82) was less than t-critical (2.0) at the degree of freedom of 38 and 5% level of significance. This implies that, there is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female Agricultural Science students taught using concept mapping method was retained.

Discussion of Findings

The results obtained from data analysis in this study shown that the use of concept mapping in instructional strategy in Agricultural science enhance better performance than the use of lecture method. This finding agrees with Sani (2017) and Kamoru (2021) who found that concept mapping facilitates the learning of scientific concepts. It is also clear from the results that male students performed significantly better than their female counterparts. The reason for this higher performance of male students could probably be that, the use of concept mapping enhanced in-depth and meaningful learning to them, which the corresponding effect showed higher performance. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Jones and Witson (2018) who found out that students taught biology with concept mapping scored significantly higher than the control group. The findings also agreed with Abdulhamid (2013) finding that concept mapping increased learning outcome and concept retention in science related areas. The result on the other hand disagreed with that of Muhammad, Mukhtar, Abdullahi and Hassan (2022) who found out that female student had improved performance than their male counterparts when exposed to learning through concept mapping. Consequently, upon these findings, therefore, concept mapping is significantly a very useful instructional strategy for increased meaningful understanding of difficult concepts and more meaningful internationalization of difficult concept in Agricultural science.

Conclusion

Base on the findings of this research work, the researcher concluded that: Concept mapping method has significant influence on the academic performance of agricultural science students in senior secondary schools in Kaduna State. There is no significant difference in the academic performances of male and female agricultural science students in the concept mapping method. The study revealed that there is statistically significant difference between the performance of students taught Agricultural science with concept mapping and those taught with lecture method in favour of students taught with concept mapping. This implies that Agricultural science teachers should be expose to training workshops and seminars on concept mapping strategy in order to update their skills of teaching concepts in Agricultural science since it has the capacity of enhancing students' performance. The study has a wider implication to teacher training institutions to as a matter of urgency in cooperate the teaching of graphic organizers which concept mapping is part of it in their teacher training schedules. This will enhance students' performance in science and national development since science and technology is at the for-front of nation building.

Recommendations

Base on the findings of this study, it was recommended among other things that:

1. Concept mapping method should be adopted by agricultural science teachers as it enhances students' academic performance.

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2. Government should equip the schools with the necessary equipment and materials needed by teachers for effective utilization of concept mapping teaching method.
3. Teachers should creative and use their initiative one using concept mapping method for better understanding by students and better academic performance.

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